

PERFORMANCE EVALUATION OF SELECTED MUTUAL FUNDS AT KOTAK SECURITIES LIMITED

Vishal¹, Amrutha², Nithin Gonsalves³, Sagar Srinivas⁴

¹Asst. Professor, Institute of Aviation Studies, Srinivas University, Mangalore

Email: vishalknayak0@gmail.com

ORCID: 0000-0001-5359-8358

²Lecturer, FMCG, Mangalore University

Email: madakaamrutha@gmail.com

³Lecturer; Presidency College Mangalore

Email: gonzanithin@gmail.com

⁴Research Scholar, College of Management and Commerce

Srinivas University Mangalore, India

ORCID: 0000-0002-1662-3769; sagarsrinivas59@gmail.com; +91 9731162400

ABSTRACT

A portfolio of securities in which funds have been invested is referred to as a "portfolio" in the financial industry. The first step when developing an inventory portfolio for an investor should be determining his financial goals. The degree of hazard tolerance is also quite significant. But, starting cash is just as important in developing a strong stock portfolio. Every portfolio needs diversification to be successful.

A frequent objective of the "portfolio investor" is to get a higher portfolio threat adjusted return when compared to investing in a single equity. When stocks are included in a portfolio, there is a chance for risk reduction and a higher return than if the money were invested in individual "equities."

The Kotak Asset Allocator Fund, according to the 5-year Average Sharpe's and Traynor's Methods, is the best plan, the analysis indicates. However, Jensen's alpha approach advises the consumer to choose the Kotak Equity Opportunities Fund plan. The Kotak Standard Multicap Fund is the final year taken into account under Sharpe's and Treynor's Method for individual schemes for 2020. Additionally, Kotak Equity Opportunities Fund is the best investment according to Jensen's alpha technique.

Keywords: Portfolio, Equities, Diversification

INTRODUCTION

In the financial world, the term "portfolio" refers to a group of securities in which money has been invested. When creating an inventory portfolio, an investor should first determine his financial objectives. (Pandow, Bilal, 2017). At the same time, the level of hazard tolerance is quite significant. On the other hand, starting funding is equally crucial in building an outstanding stock portfolio. Diversification is a critical component of every portfolio. If the investor's

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portfolio contains enough variety, he or she will be safe even in the most adverse scenarios. At the same time, a broad inventory portfolio can assist an investor in avoiding a recurring investment boom.

As comparison to financing in a single equity, a common goal of the 'portfolio investor' is to obtain a higher portfolio threat adjusted return. When equities are combined into a portfolio, there is a potential for risk discount while at the same time earning a better return than if the funds were invested in separate "equities."

The purpose of the modern "portfolio idea("Dijk, Dina & Michal, Schodl, 2015) is to maximise return while minimizing risk. In this context, research has attempted to develop a composite index to assess overall return based on chance. Sharpe, Treynor, and Jensen receive the deposit for evaluating the systematic, unsystematic, and residual hazards.

Objectives

1. To understand the market return of schemes on the basis of market indices
2. To understand the average return for 5 years with the help of Sharpe’s method
3. To understand the best return on a scheme on the basis of five schemes under Sharpe’s method
4. To understand the best return on a scheme on the basis of five schemes under Traynor’s method
5. To understand the best return on a scheme on the basis of five schemes under Jenson's'salpha method

METHODOLOGY OF RESEARCH

a. Methodology: This manuscript is based on quantitative and analytic research. Calculating under various approaches is how the approach is applied. For this review, secondary data was utilized.

b. Sources of Data

To achieve the study's goal, the research depends on both primary and secondary data. Sharpe's, Treynor's, and Jenson's average methods are employed. Furthermore, data is gathered through many published studies, publications, and central and government websites and reports.

Data Interpretation

Market Indices

Year		Close	x
2016	26101.5	26626.46	0.02
2017	26711.15	34056.83	0.275
2018	34059.99	36068.33	0.059
2019	36161.8	41253.74	0.141

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2020	41349.36	47751.33	0.155
Σx			0.65

1. Kotak Equity Opportunities Fund.

Year	X	Y	X ²	Y ²	XY
2016	0.02	0.096	0.0004	0.0092	0.0019
2017	0.275	0.349	0.0756	0.1218	0.096
2018	0.059	-0.056	0.0035	0.0031	-0.0033
2019	0.141	0.132	0.0198	0.0174	0.0186
2020	0.155	0.165	0.024	0.0272	0.0255
Total	0.65	0.686	0.1233	0.1788	0.1387
Beta	1.2756				
variance	0.0169				
SD	0.1301				

Beta	-1.2493
variance	0.1143
SD	0.338

2. Kotak Standard Multicap Fund

Year	X	Y	X ²	Y ²	XY
2016	0.02	0.94	0.0004	0.8836	0.0189

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2017	0.275	0.343	0.0756	0.1176	0.0943
2018	0.059	-0.009	0.0035	0.0001	-0.0005
2019	0.141	0.123	0.0198	0.0151	0.0173
2020	0.155	0.118	0.024	0.0139	0.0183
Total	0.65	1.515	0.1233	1.0304	0.1483

3. Kotak Infrastructure & Economic Reform Fund

Year	X	Y	X ²	Y ²	XY
2016	0.02	0.092	0.0004	0.0085	0.0019
2017	0.275	0.453	0.0756	0.2052	0.1246
2018	0.059	-0.196	0.0035	0.0384	-0.0116
2019	0.141	0.036	0.0198	0.0013	0.0051
2020	0.155	0.034	0.024	0.0012	0.0053
Total	0.65	0.419	0.1233	0.2545	0.1252
Beta	1.8198				
variance	0.0439				
SD	0.2095				

4. Kotak Emerging Equity Scheme

Year	X	Y	X ²	Y ²	XY
2016	0.020	0.104	0.000	0.011	0.002
2017	0.275	0.430	0.076	0.185	0.118
2018	0.059	-0.117	0.004	0.014	-0.007
2019	0.141	0.089	0.020	0.008	0.013
2020	0.155	0.219	0.024	0.048	0.034
Total	0.650	0.725	0.123	0.265	0.160
Beta	1.6891				

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variance	0.032
SD	0.179

Beta	0.371
variance	0.004
SD	0.06

5. Kotak Asset Allocator Fund

Year	X	Y	X²	Y²	XY
2016	0.020	0.088	0.000	0.008	0.002
2017	0.275	0.137	0.076	0.019	0.038
2018	0.059	0.044	0.004	0.002	0.003
2019	0.141	0.103	0.020	0.011	0.015
2020	0.155	0.250	0.024	0.063	0.039
Total	0.650	0.622	0.123	0.102	0.095

Average return-based evaluation

Sensex	12.994
RF	6.015

1. Sharpe "s method

Scheme	Avg return [Rp]	Beta	SD	Sharpe"s	Rank
Kotak Equity Opportunities Fund.	13.72	1.276	0.13	59.205	3
Kotak Standard Multicap Fund	30.3	-1.249	0.338	71.842	2
Kotak Infrastructure	8.38	1.82	0.209	11.289	5

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Kotak Emerging Equity Scheme	14.5	1.689	0.179	47.409	4
Kotak Asset Allocator Fund	12.44	0.371	0.069	93.116	1

Interpretation:

Based on the average returns for the last five years of various schemes under evaluation, **Kotak Asset allocator fund** has been the top performing scheme with maximum returns, which has even outperformed the market rate of returns. The next best performing scheme is the **Kotak Standard Multicap fund**. However, all other funds were not able to generate better than market returns. Finally, the **Kotak infrastructure fund** is the least performing scheme in the list.

2. Treynor method

Scheme	Avg return [Rp]	Beta	SD	Treynor	Rank
Kotak Equity Opportunities Fund.	13.72	1.276	0.13	6.040	2
Kotak Standard Multicap Fund	30.3	-1.249	0.338	-19.439	5
Kotak Infrastructure	8.38	1.82	0.209	1.300	4
Kotak Emerging Equity Scheme	14.5	1.689	0.179	5.023	3
Kotak Asset Allocator Fund	12.44	0.371	0.069	17.318	1

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Interpretation:

Based on the average returns for the last five years of various schemes under evaluation, **Kotak Asset allocator fund** has been the top performing scheme with maximum returns, which has even outperformed the market rate of returns. The next best performing scheme is **Kotak Equity Opportunities Fund**. However, all other funds were not able to generate better than market returns. Finally, the **Kotak Standard Multicap fund** is the least performing scheme in the list.

3. Jenson's alpha method

Scheme	Avg return [Rp]	Beta	SD		Rank
Kotak Equity Opportunities Fund.	13.72	1.276	0.13	50.884	1
Kotak Standard Multicap Fund.	30.3	-1.249	0.338	0.000	2
Kotak Infrastructure	8.38	1.82	0.209	-47.127	5
Kotak Emerging Equity Scheme	14.5	1.689	0.179	-46.340	4
The Kotak Asset Allocator Fund	12.44	0.371	0.069	-38.412	3

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Interpretation:

Based on the average returns for the last five years of various schemes under evaluation, **Kotak Equity Opportunities Fund** has been the top performing scheme with a highly positive return, which has even outperformed the market rate of returns. The next best performing scheme is the **Kotak Standard Multicap Fund**. However, all other funds were not able to generate better than market returns. Finally, the **Kotak Infrastructure** is the least performing scheme in the list with a highly negative value.

FINDINGS

1. Based on the average returns for the last five years of various schemes under the evaluation of Sharpe's method, **Kotak Asset Allocator Fund** has been the top performing scheme with maximum returns, which has even outperformed the market rate of returns. **The Kotak Infrastructure Fund** is the least performing scheme in the list.
2. Based on the average returns for the last five years of various schemes under evaluation, **Sharpe's Method for 2020, Kotak Standard Multicap Fund** has been the top performing scheme with maximum returns, which has even outperformed the market rate of returns. **The Kotak Asset Allocator Fund** is the least performing scheme in the list.
3. Based on the average returns for the last five years of various schemes under evaluation, the Trynors Method for 2020 **Kotak Standard Multicap Fund** has been the top performing scheme with maximum returns, which has even outperformed the market rate of returns. **The Kotak Asset Allocator Fund** is the least performing scheme in the list.
4. Based on the average returns for the last five years of various schemes under evaluation, the Jenson's alpha method for 2020 **Kotak Equity Opportunities Fund** has been the top performing scheme with a highly positive return, which has even outperformed the market rate of returns. **Kotak Infrastructure** is the least performing scheme in the list with a highly negative value.

Suggestions

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1. On the basis of average returns for the last five years of various schemes under the evaluation of Sharpe’s method, it suggests the customer go for the scheme of **Kotak Asset allocator fund** has been the top performing scheme with maximum returns, which has even outperformed the market rate of returns.
2. It also advises a customer to not invest in **Kotak Infrastructure Fund**, the least performing scheme in the list.
3. On the average returns for the last five years of various schemes under evaluation, Treynor’s it suggests the customer go for the scheme of **Kotak Asset allocator fund, which** has been the top performing scheme with maximum returns, which has even outperformed the market rate of returns.
4. It also advises a customer to not invest in **Kotak standard. The Multicap fund** is the least performing scheme in the list
5. On the average returns for the last five years of various schemes under evaluation, the_Jetsons Isalpa method suggests the customer go for the scheme of **Kotak Equity Opportunities Fund** has been the top performing scheme with highly positive returns, which has even outperformed the market rate of returns.
6. It also advises a customer to not invest in **Kotak Infrastructure**, the least performing scheme in the list with a highly negative value.
7. On the average returns for the last five years of various schemes under evaluation by **Sharpe’s Method for 2020, Kotak Standard Multicap Fund** has been the top performing scheme with maximum returns, which has even outperformed the market rate of returns.
8. **Kotak Asset Allocator Fund** is the least performing scheme in the list for 2020.

CONCLUSION

Finally, the study concludes that the **Kotak Asset Allocator Fund** is the best scheme based on the 5-year Average Sharpe’s and Traynor’s Methods. But according to Jenson's alpha method, it suggests the customer go for the scheme of **Kotak Equity Opportunities Fund**. Based on individual schemes for 2020, the last year considered on Sharpe’s and Treynor’s Method is the **Kotak Standard Multicap Fund**. And also, with reference to Jenson's alpha method, **Kotak Equity Opportunities Fund is the best investment**.

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